

SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF THE MODERN LEADER WOMEN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378370>

Abstract. *In this article, the leader identifies the peculiarities of the ayyahs in the educational process or in some other activity that is characteristic of ayyols. Adaptation is inextricably linked with psychology and is presented in development. The leadership abilities of the leader ayyols are given about the non-existence of his psychological character, the process of adaptation to work activities*

Keywords: *education, adaptation, character, feature, leader, ability.*

СОЦИАЛЬНАЯ АДАПТАЦИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ЖЕНЩИН-ЛИДЕРОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье лидер выявляет особенности айылов в образовательном процессе или в какой-либо другой деятельности, характерной для айолов. Адаптация неразрывно связана с психологией и представлена в развитии. отсутствие у него психологического характера, процесс адаптации к трудовой деятельности*

Ключевые слова: *воспитание, адаптация, характер, черта, лидер, способность.*

The leader shall have leadership skills first of all in the ayyas. And from the character of the harakater, the fact that he is sangvenik and choleric will have a balanced character. Each leader carries out activities in which the woman has a psychological adaptive nature. Psychologically, adaptation as a process and the ability to adapt, as a quality of personality, is inextricably linked with the processes taking place in modern society. Adaptation is possible only in complex self-organizing open systems that share information with the external environment. Our society has entered the post-industrial period of its development, which is characterized by a rapidly growing flow of information, a rapid quantitative and qualitative formation of the noosphere. In such conditions, the process of adaptation of a person in society, professional activity, personal life plays a special role. The duration of Stage 3 adaptation lasts about 5-6 weeks, the first month of the school year is considered the most complex adaptation period.

The success of the adaptation process is determined by the healthy state of the child and psychological readiness for study. Psychological readiness is seen as a general description of the child, in which the stages of development of psychological qualities are revealed. This, in turn, is an important basis for the adaptation of the child to school conditions in moderation and the formation of educational activities. These psychological qualities are grouped in a certain way and are seen as a component of psychological readiness for school. Socio-economic changes, Russia's integration into the world higher education system, the emergence of new values and an understanding of the importance of Education have shown the need for a new type of teacher who can quickly control the surrounding reality. Changes in society exceed the dynamics of readiness for personal adaptation. The educational system in this situation is designed to help the teacher to form the qualities necessary for the formation of a professionally qualified, competitive, active personality, able to adapt as quickly as possible to the conditions of modern reality.

Therefore, adaptation as a process and adaptation as a characteristic of the individual becomes of fundamental importance for the teacher in the process of his teaching and professional activities. In the pedagogical environment, extremely urgent problems of professional adaptation affect special teachers. Many graduates of the Faculty of special pedagogy and psychology do not go to work in Special (Correctional) educational institutions due to low wages and lack of prestige in the profession of a teacher-defectologist. A specialist in the correctional and developmental education system is a relatively new indicator of pedagogy, designed to combine a humanitarian psychologist, teacher, defectologist, social teacher into one person. This is a different generation of a teacher with fundamentally new functions and, accordingly, a different level of professional competence. A special type of teacher who not only transmits knowledge, but also creates favorable psychological and pedagogical conditions for children, creates conditions for recognizing themselves as part of a common team, for the development of creative potential, for the selection of their own educational path, based on a specific child. the next step in the development of special pedagogy. Special teachers of this type create an educational space taking into account the characteristics of the educational conditions. In such conditions, the teaching methodology must comply with the laws of both teaching and therapeutic and developmental technologies.

Despite the fact that the modern pedagogical community has pressing problems with comprehensive psychological and pedagogical support and the provision of a child with developmental problems, in practice the teacher is still "one by one" with the child's difficulties. And in many respects only the characteristics of his personality and professional training depend on the quality support and the creation of favorable conditions for the development of special children. The problem of socio-psychological adaptation of the teacher is currently the most difficult and relevant for specialists associated with the management, scientific and methodological support and control of correctional education.

Professional adaptation is manifested to a certain extent in mastering professional skills and abilities, in the formation of some professionally necessary characteristics, in the development of a stable positive attitude of an employee towards his profession. It manifests itself in familiarization with professional work, acquiring professional skills, dexterity, sufficient for the qualitative performance of functional tasks, and creativity at work. The effectiveness of professional adaptation of special female teachers directly depends on the organization of microsocial interaction: both at the level of children and at the level of their parents. An individual approach to both the child and his parents is always important. In conflict situations in the family or in the labor sphere, difficulties in establishing informal communication, violations of mechanical adaptation are noted more often than in effective social interaction.

Also, the analysis of certain environmental or environmental factors is directly related to adaptation, and in most cases, the assessment of the personal qualities of others as a factor of attraction is combined with effective mental adaptation, combining it with the assessment of the same qualities as the factors of violation. Successful professional activity in cunning depends on his special skills and training, stress resistance, communicative ability to get out of situations. In our country, the system of training and training in special women should be organized in such a way that special teachers again feel themselves belonging to the upper layers of the educational community, give a different assessment of their work, and professional activity made it possible

for them to feel comfortable where they do not work, and through it. reimbursement of psycho-emotional expenses made by special teachers.

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